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Using RFID and Industrial IoT in Manual Assembly for Data Collection and Processing in Learning Factories

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Abstract

One of the goals of Industry 4.0 is to achieve enhanced connectivity in manufacturing environments. Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) applications enable this paradigm, opening new possibilities for data collection and subsequent data processing. In this view, the Smart Mini Factory laboratory for Industry 4.0 of the Free University of Bolzano acts as a Learning Factory (LF), aiming at spreading knowledge and consciousness about Industry 4.0 technologies among students and industrial practitioners. In this work, the authors propose a retrofitting process in which a consolidated technology such as Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) is used to interconnect previously isolated workstations, transforming them into IIoT-ready entities of a cyber-physical production system (CPPS). The retrofitting process foresees the physical equipment of legacy workstations with RFID readers to identify different status of assembly operations as well as the design and implementation of a communication architecture to efficiently connect the workstations to a higher level and secure IoT platform. Thereby accurately registered data such as value adding times, idle times, and others can be used for monitoring reason and to identify improvements to the setup of the assembly line and the assembly process. The developed application is designed for being used within the assembly line of the LF. This work finally illustrates how the application is integrated in the didactic concept with the aim to learn and practice how to collect, process, and exploit digital data from production.

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1. Introduction

Cyber-physical production systems (CPPS) can be seen as crucial future trend in research as well as industry and refer to digital manufacturing [1] and Industry 4.0 [2]. It was enabled through quick developments in production engineering and information and communication technology (ICT). Developments in this context require new skills for operators in manufacturing and represent therefore a major challenge. Learning environments such as LF are an effective instrument for providing education and training platforms to develop competences in the manufacturing context [3]. The words “learning” and “factory” in the term learning factory stand for practice-oriented and innovative teaching methods with real industrial products in a realistic manufacturing environment [4]. A definition that was given as one of the earliest learning factory approaches describes them as “[...] an activity-based facility which is designed to be used across the curriculum” [5]. More recent definitions of learning factories are based on the same principle but broaden the utilization to training and education and bring out the importance of authentic environments regarding factories and close-to-reality processes [6]. Positive effects of using LF are [7]: (i) increased quality of training and education, (ii) better interdisciplinary competencies and soft skills, (iii) improved learning and application of new concepts or technologies, and (iv) a stronger link between research and industry.

The paper presents a retrofitting process in which a consolidated technology such as RFID is used to interconnect previously isolated workstations, transforming them into industrial IIoT-ready entities of a CPPS. This opens the opportunity to collect data from production and further process the resulting data to monitor the

production status and apply improvements. The proposed didactic concept sees students as protagonists in the development and installation of the presented architecture, to efficiently learn the hard- and soft-skills required to achieve goals and objectives.

After giving an introduction in the topic in Section 1, a review of the necessary theoretical background follows in Section 2. Therefore, IoT, RFID and online platforms are explained with respect to LFs. Afterwards, a description of the objectives and the research methodology are shown in Section 3. Subsequently, in Section 4, the communication architecture and the integration in the didactic concept are explained. Closing, a conclusion as well as an outlook regarding further research activities is provided in Section 5.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Internet of Things

The Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm sets new standards in the architectural design of systems and networks. IoT is defined as “*an open and comprehensive network of intelligent objects that have the capacity to auto-organize, share information, data and resources, reacting and acting in face of situations and changes in the environment*” [8]. Thanks to the adoption of technologies introduced by Industry 4.0 and the continuous digitalization process, the presence of IoT applications can be found in several sectors including, but not limited to, health care, industrial monitoring and control, domestic and home automation, smart cities, security and emergency or agriculture [9]. LFs contribute to introduce IoT in by implementing innovative demonstrators and training setups to highlight the benefits and potentials of IoT in manufacturing. As an example the authors of [10] aim at enabling training of emerging competences (i.e. cultural, methodological, social, organization and interaction competences) imposed by the digitalization trend using an IoT laboratory at the Application Center Industry 4.0 LF of the University of Potsdam, resulting in a didactic concept linked to a real-world case study. The LF at Penn State University focused on broadening the participation of students in LF’s activities by introducing Industry 4.0 related technologies, and in particular IoT [11]. With their work, they were able to establish a synergic cooperation and collaboration between students of different faculties. Given such benefits an objective of this work is to further disseminate the potential of IoT taking advantage of an LF environment.

2.2. RFID in Learning Factories

RFID technology has been widely studied and exploited in several field of applications. The RFID concept made its first appearance in 1948, it has been strongly developed during the 70’ and the 80’, and finally found worldwide applications in the new millennium. An RFID system typically consists of three actors: (i) a tag, (ii) a reader and a (iii) hosting system, typically interconnected with the enterprise systems [12]. RFID tags can be active or passive. The main difference between the two is the power source: active RFID tags are equipped with a battery while passive RFID tags are powered by induced current. Active tags have a limited life and may be larger and more expensive with respect to passive tags. Passive tags do not carry the limitations of active tags (they are smaller, cheaper and have unlimited life), but the tradeoff is represented by a limited data storage capability and a shorter operating range, which strongly depends on the design characteristics of the tag’s antenna and on the power of the reader. Several standards rule the deployment of RFID infrastructure. The most relevant have been reassumed in [13], among which the ISO/IEC 18000-6 [14] standard defines RFID air interfaces acting at various frequencies with the aim of embodying different functionalities and the IEEE 1451 [15] standards family aims to homogenizing the access to transducers overcoming interoperability. Even though the RFID technology is very diffused in industrial environments, it offers new perspectives if integrated in an IoT environment [16].

The RFID technology is also widely employed in Learning Factories, where it is used for demonstrating and teaching students and practitioners the benefits of production data collection, monitoring and analytics. The authors of [17] report the integration of an RFID-enabled Smart Factory concept within the LF at the University of Split. The same LF also conducted a performance analysis of an RFID system, to highlight some of the limitations of RFID technology [18]. As results, it has been underlined that RFID technology is less suitable for high demand of data transfer, caused by the low range of the communication field and the limited time during which the tag and the reader are close enough to successfully exchange data. In their setup, they implemented a simple Manufacturing Execution System (MES) to manage the gathered data and to monitor the performance of the systems. The LF at Stellenbosch University proposed a low cost RFID-based track and trace system developed by students for demonstrating the accessibility of the RFID technology [19], especially for small and medium enterprises (SME). We aim at developing and integrating our own demonstrator at the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, through which students and practitioners from industry learn how to use production data for planning and monitoring and how to retrofit legacy manufacturing systems.

2.3. IoT Platforms

IoT platforms are gaining importance in the Industry 4.0 landscape, where connected devices produce large amount of data, increasing the need to properly manage and exploit the collected data. The authors of [20] define an IoT platform as *“a core management solution, interface between IoT devices and end users, which provides management of devices, connections, services, and data, usually through cloud and/or fog resources. The platform delivers data storage, management, analysis, and visualization, data security management (on users and devices), integration ability, as well as auditing and payments. On the other hand, the IoT platform offers some tools, APIs, and services for building, deployment, and development of applications for IoT devices and end users”*. Taking into account this definition, an IoT platform ideally offers an all-in-one solution to better exploit the potential of IoT. In order to collect, process and visualize data in real time in trainings at the Smart Mini factory laboratory for Industry 4.0 of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, the selection of an IoT platform was necessary. Currently, the market offers an increasing number of solutions. On the one hand, big tech companies, such as Google, IBM, Amazon, and Microsoft offer proprietary solutions which better suit the needs of large companies and may be aimed to satisfy the needs of expert users. On the other hand, emerging solutions keep making their appearance on the market, targeting different audiences and offering different possibilities. For the needs of the Smart Mini factory laboratory for Industry 4.0 of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano (easy to learn and use, affordable for SMEs or open source) the IoT platform offered by ThingsBoard has been selected. ThingsBoard is an easy-to-use open source IoT platform which features user friendly interfaces (important for boosting the learning curve of first-time users), the possibility to connect to IoT devices via industrial-standard IoT protocols such as MQTT, CoAP and HTTP, a set of pre-designed dashboards and charts to visualize the gathered data, a rule engine able to process the incoming data according to specific logic, and APIs to be integrated in front-end applications. Beyond the features listed, it has to be mentioned that also a life-long license of the professional edition of ThingsBoard (advanced management of user roles, rule engine, etc.) can be purchased for a price considerably lower than the one of its more affirmed competitors.

3. Research Objectives (RO) and Methodology

The Smart Mini Factory Laboratory for Industry 4.0 of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano uses a pneumatic cylinder which consists of 22 single pieces. The cylinder can be assembled utilizing manually and electrically powered tools. Worktables based on Lean standards [21] are used to assemble the product in the most efficient way. The different worktables, arranged in line (Fig. 1), offer the opportunity for training participants to divide the individual assembly steps of the product in assembly groups. In order to keep track of cycle times, a manual time measuring takes place. Thanks to an upgrading of the traditional worktables using RFID and IoT, the time measurement should be done automatically and with higher accuracy than in the traditional approach (RO-1: automatic time measurement). The data recorded additionally should be used for real-time monitoring of further performance indicators (RO-2: real time monitoring and visualization). Further the developed technical solution should be used as a training demonstrator for retrofitting within the didactic offer of the Smart Mini Factory (RO-3: training concept for retrofitting and IIoT) a. As the Smart Mini Factory aims to train mostly SMEs an important requirement is that participants of trainings learn how to retrofit legacy systems easily and with affordable costs by taking advantage of open-source solutions (RO-4: suitable/affordable for SMEs).

The research methodology is structured in four main steps: In the first step (concept design) the didactic concept as well as the system architecture for the IoT implementation is developed on a theoretical basis. In the second step (experimental setup) the existing manual assembly line has been retrofitted equipping worktables with RFID tags and microcontrollers and configuring the online IoT platform for managing the acquired data. In the third step (testing and validation) tests have been conducted with students. As a consequence of the continuing pandemic, tests have been done also in a remote way to test how to integrate the developed application in trainings conducted in presence as well as remotely. The final fourth step (integration in didactic offer) was necessary to review and finalize the didactic concept and to prepare/adapt teaching materials and descriptions. In the following section these steps are summarized to provide the main results of this research.

Fig. 1: Training participants assembling pneumatic cylinders on the assembly line

4. Design and Implementation

4.1. Communication Architecture

The communication architecture proposed in this work is graphically described in Fig. 2. The objective of this design is to deploy stand-alone microservices on three distinct levels to make the system more understandable, scalable, and maintainable: (1) the physical level, (2) the middleware level and (3) the Business Intelligence (BI) level. On the physical layer, each workstation of the line is equipped with two RFID readers, one on the left side and one on the right side of the operator and a microcontroller (see “Edge Node” in Fig. 2) that manages the exchange of data with the RFID readers with the middleware (see “Master Node” in Fig. 2). In addition, each semifinished product is equipped with a unique RFID identifier. For this application, RFID is preferred to Near Field Communication (NFC) in as much the communication is unidirectional, aiming at transferring information from the RFID tags to the RFID readers. The operator has to badge the semifinished product on the left RFID reader when he/she starts to manipulate it and has to badge it on the right RFID reader when he/she terminates the assembly sequence and passing it over to the next workstation. By doing so, it is possible to record timestamps at which the semifinished product undergoes certain production stages. Each recorded timestamp is associated with the unique RFID identifier that triggered the recording and is subsequently sent to the Master Node. The master node is then in charge of sharing the received information with all the other nodes connected to it, both upstream (to the online IoT platform and the Business Intelligence level) and down-stream (to the workstations’ nodes). In other words, a democratization of the communication is performed, as all the actors connected to the network are always aware about the information exchanged by all its elements. In the same way, messages or alerts generated by the online IoT platform are sent to the Master node, which will then broadcast them to all the workstations’ nodes and will displayed on LCD screens. In this view, the assembly line becomes “smart”, because the generated data allows actors of the network to perform analytics and to deduce possible actions for improvement.

Fig. 2: Communication architecture

For example, workstations’ nodes equipped with microcontrollers act as edge computing devices for autonomously managing the digital work instructions on the monitor of each workstation or to suggesting the operator with possible flying modification to the assembly cycle with the objective of homogenizing the takt time of all workstations, thus reducing idle times and the overall lead time. Thanks to the rule engine that many online

IoT platform offer, it is possible to provide both long- and short-term data analysis and visualization of metrics to allow operators and/or production managers identifying improvement potentials. Different standardized communication protocols can be employed to establish a secure and effective connection among the Edge nodes, the Master node and the Online IoT platform, also considering those protocols that are already in use in the LF environment.

4.2. Implementation and Testing

In this paragraph, the implementation of the communication architecture explained in Section 4.1 is going to be described. As explained in Section 3, for this specific implementation in the Smart Mini Factory, it has been decided to transform an already existing assembly line into an IoT based one. For maintaining the same setup and (for didactic reasons) being able to make comparisons between traditional assembly and IoT-enabled assembly, the following hardware components have been used for the retrofitting of the line: 4x Raspberry Pi 4, 4GB RAM; 6x Adafruit PN532 NFC/RFID Arduino Shields; 1x ThingsBoard License (online IoT platform). Each of the workstations has been equipped with a Raspberry Pi 4 and two Adafruit Pn532 NFC/RFID Arduino shields, which are physically wired the one to the other. A general microservice is deployed in Python for collecting timestamps and relative information (semifinished product ID and RFID reader ID) as well as for sending/receiving data to/from the Master Node. Another microservice runs on the Edge Node for autonomously managing the assembly instructions displayed on an LCD screen. The communication protocol employed for the data exchange among the Edge Nodes and the Master Node (and vice versa) is MQTT, considering its ease of use and its diffusion in the other existing applications inside the laboratory. The Master Node also runs on a Raspberry Pi 4 and is a passive actor, who receives data from a node and broadcasts it to all other nodes, up- and downstream. For this reason, on the Master Node a single, multipurpose Python microservice operates as listener and as broadcaster. For maintaining system homogeneity, MQTT protocol is employed also for interconnecting the Master Node and the ThingsBoard IoT online platform. ThingsBoard is used to receive, manage, analyze, and display data in easy-to-comprehend dashboards and infographics. In addition, a rule engine allows system designers to set autonomous controls and consequent autonomous feedback and self-optimization rules.

The implemented solution has been tested to verify its stability and robustness in two ways with students. Graduate students have been involved in testing the development and implementation of the proposed IIoT solution and configuration of ThingsBoard. Undergraduate students have tested the functioning of time measurement as well as monitoring functionality to deduce actions for improvements in the setup and the assembly process. Feedbacks of the testing have not been analyzed with quantitative research (due to a not statistically representative number of participants) but with qualitative research using semi-structured interviews. Feedbacks have been used for reviewing the technical/didactic concept. In particular, tests runs highlighted unpredicted latency in data transmission between RFID readers and the Master Node. After further investigation, it has been found that the reported issue arose from a bug in the workstations' nodes, which has been solved immediately,

4.3. Integration of the Didactic Concept

In the case of the Smart Mini Factory the proposed technical solution has been implemented in a demonstrator for lean and manual assembly. With the developed technical solution, students and practitioners can be trained in lean/manual assembly in a digitalized way, while learning in addition the basic concepts of IoT, data management, and the subsequent analysis and visualization of the data. Through the analysis of accurately registered data, e.g., value adding times, idle times, etc., both real-time and long-term improvements can be deduced from the target groups to improve the assembly cycle design and the setup of the assembly line. Th didactic concept does foresee to offer the following didactic trainings to different target groups and different EQF-levels (European Qualification Framework):

- Undergraduate Training in Lean and Smart Assembly (EQF Level 6): Integration of the demonstrator in the practical exercise of the course “Production Systems and Industrial Logistics” focusing on using the data retrieved from the online IoT platform for monitoring/evaluation of different assembly strategies.
- Undergraduate Training in Digital Production Planning (EQF Level 6): Integration of the demonstrator in the practical exercise of the course “Digital Production Planning” focusing on using the IIoT monitoring and data for production planning purposes and demonstrating digital tools in production planning.
- Graduate Training in IIoT and Retrofitting (EQF Level 7): Integration of the demonstrator in the practical exercise of the course “Digital Manufacturing and Simulation” focusing on the technical development, engineering and implementation/testing of IIoT solutions for retrofitting of legacy systems.

- Training for professionals in Digital Production Management (EQF Level 6-7): Combination of the before mentioned teaching contents in a 2-day course for practitioners teaching them in retrofitting of legacy systems, collecting real-time data, analyzing the data and exploiting available data in production.

Another advantage of the proposed IIoT concept is its suitability for being used in remote training sessions. This may not only counteract situations like Covid-19 but also has positive effects in increasing flexibility for organizing trainings as well as minimizing the impact on the environment through a reduced need for traveling.

5. Conclusions and Outlook

Regarding the performance of the implemented solution the demonstrator is now used for autonomous time measurement (RO-1) as well as a general real-time monitoring (RO-2) of the manual assembly line of the Smart Mini Factory. Many companies struggle to implement IIoT on their shop floor due to missing competences and practice of their technicians and production engineers. Therefore, this work contributes to providing a teaching concept and system architecture for teaching retrofitting to engineering students as well as practitioners from industry (RO-3). The technical solution for retrofitting of manual assembly workstations proposed in this paper can be implemented with expenses under 250 Euro and does only require basic/medium skills in microcontrollers and Python coding. Thus, it fulfills RO-4 regarding accessibility for SMEs. A limitation in the current work is the missing consideration of data security issues when implementing the concept in real industrial use cases. Thus, the research team will work in a next step in addressing also cyber security issues in the training offer and demonstrators of the Smart Mini Factory.

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References

- [1] D. Chen, S. Heyer, S. Ibbotson, K. Salonitis, J. G. Steingrímsson, and S. Thiede, "Direct digital manufacturing: definition, evolution, and sustainability implications," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 107, pp. 615–625, 2015.
- [2] H. Kagermann, W. Wahlster, J. Helbig, A. Hellinger, and R. Karger, "Im Fokus: das Zukunftsprojekt Industrie 4.0: Handlungsempfehlungen zur Umsetzung," *Bericht der Promotorengruppe Kommunikation. Forschungsunion*, 2012.
- [3] M. Tisch, C. Hertle, J. Cachay, E. Abele, J. Metternich, and R. Tenberg, "A systematic approach on developing action-oriented, competency-based Learning Factories," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 7, pp. 580–585, 2013.
- [4] K. Y. H. Lim, P. Zheng, and C.-H. Chen, "A state-of-the-art survey of Digital Twin: techniques, engineering product lifecycle management and business innovation perspectives," *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 1313–1337, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10845-019-01512-w.
- [5] J. Lamancusa, J. Jorgensen, J. Ratner, and J. Zayas-Castro, "The Learning Factory: Curriculum Integration of Design and Manufacturing," in *Proc. of the Fourth World Conference on Engineering Education*, 1995, pp. 15–20.
- [6] E. Abele, R. Tenberg, J. Wennemer, and J. Cachay, "Kompetenzentwicklung in Lernfabriken für die Produktion," *Zeitschrift für wirtschaftlichen Fabrikbetrieb*, vol. 105, no. 10, pp. 909–913, 2010.
- [7] E. Abele, J. Metternich, and M. Tisch, *Learning Factories - Concepts, Guidelines, Best-Practice Examples*.
- [8] S. M. A. Group et al., "Internet of Things (IoT): A Literature Review," *Journal of Computer and Communications*, vol. 03, no. 05, Art. no. 05, 2015, doi: 10.4236/jcc.2015.35021.
- [9] S. Balaji, K. Nathani, and R. Santhakumar, "IoT Technology, Applications and Challenges: A Contemporary Survey," *Wireless Pers Commun*, vol. 108, no. 1, pp. 363–388, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s11277-019-06407-w.
- [10] N. Gronau, A. Ullrich, and M. Teichmann, "Development of the industrial IoT competences in the areas of organization, process, and interaction based on the learning factory concept," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 9, pp. 254–261, 2017.
- [11] D. R. Spillane, J. Menold, and M. B. Parkinson, "Broadening participation in learning factories through industry 4.0," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 45, pp. 534–539, 2020.
- [12] C. M. Roberts, "Radio frequency identification (RFID)," *Computers & security*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 18–26, 2006.
- [13] T. S. López, "RFID and sensor integration standards: State and future prospects," *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 207–213, 2011.
- [14] "ISO/IEC 18000-6:2013 - Information technology — Radio frequency identification for item management — Part 6: Parameters for air interface communications at 860 MHz to 960 MHz General." [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/59644.html>
- [15] K. Lee, "IEEE 1451: A standard in support of smart transducer networking," in *Proceedings of the 17th IEEE Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference [Cat. No. 00CH37066]*, 2000, vol. 2, pp. 525–528.
- [16] Y. Duroc and S. Tedjini, "RFID: A key technology for Humanity," *Comptes Rendus Physique*, vol. 19, no. 1–2, pp. 64–71, 2018.
- [17] M. Mladineo, I. Veza, N. Gjeldum, M. Crnjac, A. Aljinovic, and A. Basic, "Integration and testing of the RFID-enabled Smart Factory concept within the Learning Factory," *Procedia manufacturing*, vol. 31, pp. 384–389, 2019.
- [18] N. Gjeldum, M. Mladineo, M. Crnjac, I. Veza, and A. Aljinovic, "Performance analysis of the RFID system for optimal design of the intelligent assembly line in the learning factory," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 23, pp. 63–68, 2018.
- [19] L. Louw and M. Walker, "Design and implementation of a low cost RFID track and trace system in a learning factory," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 23, pp. 255–260, 2018.
- [20] M. Asemani, F. Abdollahi, and F. Jabbari, "Understanding IoT platforms: towards a comprehensive definition and main characteristic description," in *2019 5th International Conference on Web Research (ICWR)*, 2019, pp. 172–177.
- [21] D. T. Matt, "Application of Axiomatic Design principles to control complexity dynamics in a mixed-model assembly system: a case analysis," *International Journal of Production Research*, vol. 50, no. 7, pp. 1850–1861, 2012.